

INTELLIGENT ELECTRO-RHEOLOGICAL DAMPERS FOR ACTIVE VIBRATION CONTROL: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Intelligent electro-rheological (ER) fluid dampers were designed and tested for vibration control of mechanical systems. The main focus of this study was to assess the vibration suppression due to the change in the damping of the ER fluid dampers by using an on/off controller. Experiments were conducted to examine the forced vibration control of a thin, cantilever, metallic beam. The dampers which were located at the tip of the beam were activated by applying a small electric current, on the order of mA, to the ER fluid. It was found that a single-electrode ER damper can reduce vibration, considerably. It was also demonstrated that by increasing the number of electrodes the voltage requirement sharply decreases.

Keywords: intelligent, damper, ER fluids, vibration control

1. INTRODUCTION

ER fluids consist of solid particles dispersed in a nonconductive oil where in most fluids small amount of water is also added. The suspended particles change their random configuration to an aligned and relatively regular chain-like pattern in the presence of an electric field. Winslow [1] is the first who reported the electro-rheological (Winslow's) effect. The rheology of ER fluids can be changed upon the application of a low amperage current by over a hundred-fold. The effect is on the order of milliseconds and is reversible. Depending on the condition of the fluid, the resistance to flow can increase and in some cases the fluid may be converted to a jel-like solid [2-7]. The fast response time of ER

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fluids to the applied current provides many design possibilities in different engineering disciplines, such as, in automobile suspension systems, clutches, robotic devices, automatic valves, etc. [8-13].

ER fluids also can potentially be used in dampers to suppress vibration in civil structures that undergo seismic and wind excitations. Large-scale civil structures, such as bridges, under earthquakes, strong winds and heavy traffic loads should have the ability of dissipating considerable amount of energy. Although passive mechanical energy absorption devices such as base isolations, friction and viscoelastic dampers, and bracing systems offer limited capability to suppress the vibration of structures, they lack to control the motion under severe environmental dynamic loads. The feasibility of active control systems for large structures has been demonstrated for certain cases by using systems such as variable stiffness devices [14], and active bracing [15,16] in the laboratory testing. Full-scale implementations of some active systems have begun in the US and Japan [17,18]. The use of hybrid (passive/active) control systems [19,20] is more attractive because the passive system provides a steady dissipation capability while the active system can control the transient dynamic motion.

In this work the performance of small-scale, single- and multi-electrode ER fluid dampers is experimentally investigated. The focus of the paper is on the proof-of-the-concept study by examining the active control of a cantilever beam under forced vibration. In the following, the damper design, experimental set up and experimental results are presented.

2. TEST APPARATUS

Single- and triple-electrode ER fluid dampers were designed and built in small scales to suppress the vibration of a thin cantilever beam under forced vibration. A photo of the single-electrode damper is shown in Figure 1. An aluminum rod is placed at the center of the single-electrode damper to transmit the force directly to the plaxy-glass cylindrical casing. The rod which is the ground electrode is constrained to move axially by a bearing at the top and a small shaft and a cylinder at the bottom. Attached to the rod is a brass hollow cylinder electrode which is fitted through the casing. Inside the damper is filled with ER fluid. The fluid between the electrodes is electrically stressed by the voltage applied to the damper using a 408B Fluke High Voltage Power Supply. The gap between the electrodes is 2mm, and the effecting stress area, (i.e, the exposed surface area of the electrodes) is $4.30 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2$.

The performance of both single- and triple-electrode ER fluid dampers were examined by the experimental set up illustrated in Figure 2. The damper was connected to a thin, cantilever, aluminum beam with a rectangular cross-section. The beam was clamped to an All American Vibration Fatigue Testing Machine and was shaken at a frequency of 10 Hz. The vibration at the tip of the beam was measured by using two independent measurement set ups: 1) A laser, a laser sensor, a 12-bit analog-to-Digital I/O DAS-20 Keithly Metrabyte data acquisition board, and a 386 IBM computer, and 2) an accelerometer, a noise filter, an amplifier and an oscilloscope.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In the following, experimental data are presented for the suppression of the forced vibration control of a cantilever beam using both single- and triple-electrode ER fluid dampers. The beam was excited by a shake table and the frequency of the motion was 10 Hz for all cases. The length of the beam was selected such that the motion of the beam could be considered a rigid body motion. The amount of current required for all experiments was 0.5 mA. Consistent results were obtained by both the laser displacement and piezoelectric accelerometer sensors.

First, the on-line time response of the single-electrode ER fluid damper to the applied voltage was examined by using an on/off controller. Within 0.1 second, the applied voltage was increased from 0 to 3.4 Kv/mm, as shown in Figure 3. It turned out that the time response was about a fraction of a second. The drop of the output voltage was measured by the laser displacement sensor. This output was a measure of decrease in amplitude of the motion which was about 40%. One of the major challenges in this experiment was to reduce the amount of the noise in the output data. The laser displacement sensor is very sensitive to lights and electromagnetic fields.

Next, series of experiments were conducted on single- and triple-electrode ER fluid dampers to assess the vibration control. Some of the results are presented in Figures 4-9. These figures are the photos of the output voltage on the oscilloscope which is a measure of the acceleration of the tip of the beam. Figures 4-6 demonstrate the decay of the motion due to the voltage increase from 0 to 1.43 and to 2.29 Kv/mm, repressively. As can be seen, the out put voltage drops sharply to 1.4 Volts for 1.43 Kv/mm and to 1.2 Volts for 2.29 Kv/mm. Figures 7-9 show the performance of the triple-electrode ER fluid damper for 0, 4, and 8 Kv/mm, respectively. It should be noted that the output voltage scale on these figures are different than those of Figures 4-6. The decay of the motion compare to the single-electrode damper is considerable. By comparing Figures 7 and 9, it turns out that the acceleration is reduced about 35%

Finally, comparisons were made on the performance of the single- and triple electrode ER fluid dampers. Figures 10 and 11 demonstrate the actual and the normalized suppression of the motion by increasing the applied voltage for these dampers. In Figure 10 it is clear that the triple-electrode damper can reduce vibration much better than the single-electrode one. This is due to the larger area of the contact between the surface of the electrodes and the ER fluid. Even when no voltage is applied the triple-electrode damper demonstrates higher vibration reduction. This is due to more friction area between the fluid and the electrodes. Figure 11 shows a normalized out put for the two dampers in which only the effect of the applied voltage is considered. Again, it can be seen that the triple-electrode damper require much less voltage.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The performance of single- and triple-electrode ER fluid dampers was investigated by suppression of the forced vibration of a cantilever beam using an on/off controller. Vibration reduction of more than 50% were obtained. It was shown that the increase in the number of electrodes on the control of the vibration was considerable.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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6. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Close up view of the single-electrode ER fluid damper and laser sensor at the tip of the beam.

Figure 2. Schematic of the experimental setup.

Figure 3. Performance of the single-electrode ER fluid damper using an on/off controller.

Figure 4. Response of the tip of the cantilever beam to the forced vibration (10 Hz) using the single-electrode ER fluid damper (0.0 Kv/mm).

Figure 5. Response of the tip of the cantilever beam to the forced vibration (10 Hz) using the single-electrode ER fluid damper (1.43 Kv/mm).

Figure 6. Response of the tip of the cantilever beam to the forced vibration (10 Hz) using the single-electrode ER fluid damper (2.29 Kv/mm).

Figure 7. Response of the tip of the cantilever beam to the forced vibration (10 Hz) using the triple-electrode ER fluid damper (0.0 Kv/mm).

Figure 8. Response of the tip of the cantilever beam to the forced vibration (10 Hz) using the triple-electrode ER fluid damper (4.0 Kv/mm).

Figure 9. Response of the tip of the cantilever beam to the forced vibration (10 Hz) using the triple-electrode ER fluid damper (8.0 Kv/mm).

Figure 10. Comparison between the performance of single- and triple-electrode ER fluid dampers.

Figure 11, Comparison between the performance of single- and triple-electrode ER fluid dampers on a normalized scale.

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